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KEYWORDS: *capital investment, financial investments, real investments, intellectual investments*

INTRODUCTION: Since the first years of the state independence, Uzbekistan has determined a specific direction for the development of the national economy. And the role of investment in the development of the economy is incomparable.

There is a wide variety of opinions among economic scientists about the economic content and nature of investments.

The law of the Republic of Uzbekistan “on investments and investment activities” of December 25, 2019 defines investment as: “investments are tangible and intangible assets and rights to them, including rights to intellectual property objects, as well as reinvestitions, which are made by the investor on the basis of risks to objects of social sphere, entrepreneurial, scientific and other types of activity.

Thus, "investment" is understood as all types of property, financial and integrated assets that are poured by investors into various sectors and other sectors of the economy within the framework of the law in order to obtain future income (profit) or achieve social effect.

There is no specific definition of investment. In particular, prof. D. G'. Gezibekov interpreted the economic content and essence of investments as a financial category, describing it as follows: “the content of investments will consist in obtaining funds from clear and reliable sources, mobilizing them reasonably, maintaining the value of capital, taking into account the level of rickshaws, and obtaining the intended effect.”

Prof. N.H. Heydarov gives the following definition of the meaning and essence of investments: “investment is the expenditure of their wealth on any object of entrepreneurship within the framework of the law, regardless of the form of ownership, for the purpose of obtaining economic and social effect of individuals and legal entities or the state operating on an entrepreneurial basis.”

It has been described by local economists-scientists as: "investments are expressed as any means by which money can be deposited, given the maintenance, increase or provision of a positive amount of income". Author of the textbook "investitsii", professor A.Neshitoy describes the content of investments as follows: "the long-term placement of funds (capital) aimed at the implementation of entrepreneurial projects, socio-economic programs and innovation projects in different sectors of one country or another in order to obtain profit or achieve other benefits."

The economic essence of the term investment was further described by a number of Russian and Uzbek scientists as follows:

- "investments reflect all types of property and intellectual property that are included in the objects of the investment sphere in order to obtain economic benefits and social benefits" ;

- "investments are understood as the sum of expenses that are carried out in the form of a targeted investment of capital for a certain period in various sectors and sectors of the economy, objects of entrepreneurship and other types of activity in order to obtain profit (income) and achieve a positive social effect, like the individual goals of investors" ;

- "investment manifests itself as a long-term investment of private or public capital in various sectors of the national and foreign economy in order to obtain profit (income)" ;

- "the concept of investment means the long-term introduction of capital, funds into some kind of enterprise, organization, long-term projects and the like in order to make a profit."

Investments in a broad sense manifest themselves as the further increase in funds and resources and their mobilization in order to obtain economic results or other planned results (social, environmental and other effects).

Of the foreign economists-scientists, he was a Sharp, K. Eklund, Campbell R. McConnell, Stanley L. The likes of Brue have set out different definitions of the meaning of investment. Including the Nobel laureate in economics (1990) U. According to Sharp: "investments are the abandonment of a certain value at the present time in order to obtain value in the future (possibly non-traditional)". The meaning of the term "investing" is interpreted in this way: "in order to make a profit in the future, today is a separation from money", and they calculate that it is possible to invest funds or real-world financial assets. They see the content of the term investing in "parting" with money today in order to make a profit in the future.

Swedish economist-scientist K. Eklund believes: "investment is something that is left to tomorrow to have more consumption conditions in the future. Part of it is consumer items that are now left in stock without being used, and the other part is resources that are aimed at expanding this production" .

"The term investment can be defined as the placement of capital in its various forms for the purpose of future growth" . "Investment is the abandonment of today's consumption for the purpose of further growth of investment" . "Investment is the current increase in the value of capital investment that appears during the production period. It is considered an unused part of the profits of the time for consumption" .

Investments-means the cost of money or other funds today to make a profit in the future. For example, when taking shares, the proceeds from owning them are equally affected by the risk of investment in time. Even the time it takes to read a textbook (even if you don't think it's worth it) is an investment. An important component of national wealth is the main funds in enterprises and organizations, in the branches of the national economy.

For a long time (more than a year), material assets, which are also valid in the field of material production, in the field of non-production, and are also used for leasing, are the

main tools. The main tools include buildings, structures, conductors, machinery and equipment, vehicles, measuring instruments, Computing Machinery, production and farm inventory, working and productive animals, perennial trees, capital investments spent to improve the reclamation of the land, etc.

CONCLUSION

investments form the backbone of economic progress and development. By spurring capital formation, job creation, technological advancements, and income generation, investments contribute to overall economic growth. Understanding the economic content and essence of investments helps individuals and policymakers make informed decisions to foster a conducive investment environment. By focusing on key factors, such as stability, market potential, access to capital, infrastructure, and social stability, economies can attract investments and reap their benefits.

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